

Coverage and Capacity Performance Degradation on a Co-Located Network Involving CDMA2000 and WCDMA @1.9GH

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Abstract : Abstract — Coverage and capacity performance in a cellular network determines the system potentials. If the coverage radius is limited, end users suffer poor service quality, if the system capacity reduces, fewer subscribers will be accommodated. This paper investigated the performance effects of the noise rise caused by the spurious emission from a co-located jammer involving downlink frequency of CDMA2000 and uplink frequency of WCDMA operating at 1.9GHz. Measurements were carried out to evaluate the impact on the coverage radius and the system capacity.

Keywords : Capacity, Co-location, Coverage, Noise rise.

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